

Consideration of Future Consequences-Immediate (CFC-Immediate) and Consideration of Future Consequences-Future (CFC-Future): Overview

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Abstract

This study investigates how a specific domain consideration of future consequences i.e., consideration of future consequences-Immediate (CFC-Immediate) and consideration of future consequences-Future (CFC-Future) asymmetrically associate and interact with perceived risk and perceived security as trade-off constructs in predicting continuance intention to use mobile commerce.

Keywords: *Consideration of future consequences*

1. Introduction

Previous studies have considered the significant evolvement of mobile devices and mobile internet technologies in recent year (Hanafizadeh, Behboudi, Koshksaray and Tabar, 2014, Malaquias and Hwang, 2016) as an important facilitator of the development and proliferation of mobile applications and mobile business (Celik, 2016, Lu, 2014). As a result, mobile commerce has emerged as an alternative and modern type of shopping among consumers (Khoi et al., 2018, Phong, Khoi and Le, 2018, Shao, Zhang, Li and Guo, 2019). Because mobile commerce use mobile devices and wireless internet connection, the key benefits of this modern type of commerces are ubiquity, accessibility, convenience, localization, instant connectivity, time sensitivity and security (Anil, Ting, Moe and Jonathan, 2003, Nassuora, 2013, Sanakulov and Karjaluto, 2015, Zhang, Zhu and Liu, 2012). Also, mobile commerce is faster, more powerful and more effective than computer-based e-commerce (Hsieh, 2014).

With no exception, the development of mobile commerce depends on the attraction of new consumers (Ovčjak, Heričko and Polančič, 2015, Sanakulov and Karjaluto, 2015, Zhang et al., 2012). This issue also attracts the interest of academia all over the world. Indeed, previous studies have revealed that one of the main topics is what determinants of customer intention to use this modern type of shopping. Previous studies have categorized online shopping into mobile commerce, electronic commerce, social commerce and Facebook commerce (Khoi et al., 2018, Lam, Yeung, Lo and Cheng, 2019, Wu, Shen and Chang, 2015). While mobile commerce refers to conducting transactions on mobile devices, electronic commerce is defined as conducting an online transaction via the Internet in a computer-mediated environment (Vladimir, 1996), social commerce can be seen as a subset of electronic commerce that includes conducting various types of commercial activities on social media (Lam et al., 2019) such as Facebook, Twitter. As such Facebook commerce is social commerce that is conducted in a specific social network of Facebook (Chen, Su and Widjaja, 2016). With the increasing competition between mobile commerce and other types of commerce, maintaining existing consumers seems to be more effective and efficient (Yuan, Liu, Yao and Liu, 2014, Zhou, 2013c, Zhou, 2013e, Zhou, 2014).

In other words, nurturing and fostering continuance intention of mobile commerce use also is a significant issue to discover (Bhattacharjee, Perols and Sanford, 2015, Yuan et al., 2014, Zhou, 2014). However, previous studies in a mobile commerce context mainly focus on initial adoption while continuance adoption or repurchase loyalty receives less attention and interest (Shao et al., 2019, Zhou, 2014). Also, prior studies have largely adopted technology's characteristics driving factors that are derived from well-established models such as the technology acceptance model (TAM; Davis, 1989), innovation diffusion theory (IDT; Rogers, 1995) and the unified theory of acceptance and usage of technology (UATUT; Venkatesh, Morris, Davis and Davis, 2003) to increase the predictive power of models explaining and predicting consumer continuance intention to use mobile commerce (Shao et al., 2019, Zhou, 2013b, Zhou, 2013e, Zhou, 2014). Most of prior research focus on either promotion or barrier factors, for example, Chong (2015) adopts two constructs of technology acceptance

model, which are perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, to explain an increase in continuance intention to use mobile commerce while Zhou (2014) uses two variables (i.e., Information quality and system quality) derived from the model of information system success to explain a decrease in continuance usage of mobile payment. However, there still a lack of studies that simultaneously investigates both promotion and barrier factors, for example risk and security to form a more comprehensive pictures of if and how opposite determinants are related to continuance intention to use mobile commerce (Hanafizadeh et al., 2014, Malaquias and Hwang, 2016, Phong et al., 2018). From the practical perspective, those understanding provide policy makers and companies with insights into the development of appropriate marketing strategies to promote the mobile commerce services use (Hsieh, 2014).

Furthermore, previous studies have documented that consumer behavior is affected by individual differences (Hong, Lin and Hsieh, 2017, Mohamed, Hussein, Hidayah Ahmad Zamzuri and Haghshenas, 2014, Wang, Ngai and Wei, 2012). In general, individual difference factors have been extensively divided into personality, cognitive style, and demographic/situational variables (Hirschberg, 1978). Among them, personality traits are stable characteristics that have important roles in explaining behavior (Liu, Zhao, Chau and Tang, 2015). Personality traits such as Big Five and personal values, perceived values, risk-taking propensity, personal innovativeness are adopted to explain continuance to use innovative products and services (Hong et al., 2017, Mohamed et al., 2014, Wang et al., 2012). However, time perspective - one personality traits factor that have potential to explain behavioral continuance intention – is largely ignored in a mobile commerce context (Joireman and King, 2016). From the academic perspective, the investigating of if and how time perspective is related to continuance intention to use mobile commerce contributes to the understanding of the relationship between personality traits and behavioral intention while from the practical aspect, this understanding would provide managers with more insights into consumer segmenting and targeting (Olsen and Tuu, 2017, Pozolotina and Olsen, 2019).

2. Literature review

Consideration of future consequences CFC is defined as the extent to which individuals consider the potential distant outcomes (i.e., immediate and future benefits) of their current behaviors and the extent to which they are influenced by these potential outcomes (Strathman et al., 1994). Most previous studies also adapt the conceptualization and operationalization of CFC including two distinct factors, which are CFC-Immediate and CFC-Future (Arnocky, Milfont and Nicol, 2013, Joireman, Shaffer, Balliet and Strathman, 2012, Olsen and Tuu, 2017). Recently well-established studies in different areas such as food behaviors (Dassen, Houben and Jansen, 2015, Dassen, Jansen, Nederkoorn and Houben, 2016, Olsen and Tuu, 2017) or pro-environmental behaviors (Arnocky et al., 2013, Joireman et al., 2012, van Beek, Antonides and Handgraaf, 2013) have focused on consumers' time perspective to generate interventions toward expected outcomes for both individuals and societies. Also, previous studies suggest that CFC can be regarded as a domain-specific concept since individuals can be time-oriented in some spheres of life, but not in others (McKay, Perry, Cole and Magee, 2017, Olsen and Tuu, 2017, van Beek et al., 2013). Furthermore, CFC has been largely ignored in mobile commerce context. Therefore, while in responding to a call for research on the unique contributions of CFC-Immediate and CFC-Future (Joireman et al., 2008, Joireman and King, 2016), the current research also contributes the the existing literature by extending the two-factor structure of CFC into a domain-specific immediate and future time perspective of a new context of mobile commerce.

Consumers' continuance intention to use mobile commerce is an important behavior that has attracted substantial attention from both e-commerce academia and practitioners (Lin and Shih, 2008, Shao et al., 2019, Zhou, 2011). It is defined as an individual's subjective probability to continue using mobile commerce (Bhattacharjee, 2001a, Bhattacharjee et al., 2015). Continuance intention to use mobile commerce could reflect a consideration of a trade-off between focusing on negative results/risk (e.g., monetary loss, status loss, privacy threat) versus emphasizing positive outcomes/security (e.g., service personalization, convenience, secured financial transaction) (Ashraf, Razzaque and Thongpapanl, 2016, Kalinic and Marinkovic, 2015) that depend on individual differences regarding their immediate and future perspectives (Joireman et al., 2008, Joireman, Kees and Sprott, 2010, Joireman et al., 2012, Joireman, Strathman and Balliet, 2006, Olsen and Tuu, 2017).

Therefore, this study helps to respond to a call for filling the gaps in exploring individual differences to predict consumer behaviors in mobile commerce context (Ovčjak et al., 2015, Sanakulov and Karjaluoto, 2015, Zhang et al., 2012). Particularly, the relative role of CFC-Immediate and CFC-Future in relation with perceived risk and perceived security, to predict consumer continuance intention to use mobile commerce is investigated in the current study. A knowledge on how to shift consumers from a focus on immediate benefits and negative/risk perceptions to an emphasis on future benefits and positive/security perspective can be important for developing effective messages to convince consumers in increasing mobile commerce usage.

Both perceived risk and perceived security are important constructs in consumer literature, particularly in a mobile commerce area (Flavián and Guinalú, 2006, Hartono et al., 2014, Schierz, Schilke and Wirtz, 2010). While perceived risk has long been defined as negative perceptions and losses (Ovčjak et al., 2015, Sanakulov and Karjaluoto, 2015, Zhang et al., 2012), perceived security has emerged to be understood as positive cognitions and potential prospect of online services (Flavián and Guinalú, 2006, Hartono et al., 2014, Schierz et al., 2010). According to the regulatory focus theory (Higgins, 1997), perceived risk is considered to be closely associated with prevention focus (Ovčjak et al., 2015, Sanakulov and Karjaluoto, 2015, Zhang et al., 2012), while perceived security is usually connected to promotion focus (Flavián and Guinalú, 2006, Hartono et al., 2014, Schierz et al., 2010, Shin, 2009). Since individuals with CFC-Immediate tend to focus more on losses, negative results, pessimistic thoughts and prevention orientation, while those with CFC-Future tend to focus on gains, positive consequences, optimistic thoughts and promotion orientation as guides for their current actions (Joireman et al., 2012), CFC-Immediate and CFC-Future may have asymmetric effects on perceived risk versus perceived security. Therefore, this study makes an effort to extend the previous studies on CFCs (e.g., Olsen and Tuu, 2017) in a mobile commerce context by exploring if and why both CFC-Immediate and CFC-Future can asymmetrically influence perceived risk and perceived security. The investigation of asymmetric impacts of CFC-Immediate and CFC-Future on both perceived risk and perceived security is expected to provide a deeper insight into how to consolidate positive benefits and to weaken negative perceptions or losses to promote consumers' expected behaviors (e.g., Olsen and Tuu, 2017).

Furthermore, it is more likely that CFC-Immediate better fits with perceived risk than with perceived security while CFC-Future is more congruent with perceived security than perceived risk (Aaker and Lee, 2006, Higgins, 1997, Higgins, Friedman, Harlow, Idson, Ayduk and Taylor, 2001). Therefore, CFC-Immediate would make consumers become more and less sensitive to risk and security respectively, meanwhile, consumers with CFC-Future tend to be less sensitive to risk and more sensitive to security. This implies CFC-Immediate and CFC-Future could have contradicting interactions with perceived risk and security to influence behavioral consequences (c.f. Kees, Burton and Tangari, 2010, Strathman et al., 1994). For this reason, this study goes a further step to explore these moderating effects to give a more comprehensive picture of if and why CFC can interact with perceived risk and security to impact on continuance intention to use mobile commerce. A more comprehensive understanding of perceived risk and perceived security is also provided by structuring those two constructs as reflective second-order construct versus formative second-order construct (Hartono et al., 2014, Park and Tussyadiah, 2016).

This study has some important contributions by combining CFC-Immediate and CFC-Future with perceived risk and perceived security to explain consumer continuance intention to use mobile commerce by answering some ignored questions in a mobile commerce context. By addressing these questions, this study contributes to the body of knowledge regarding the different effects of an important individual difference characteristic (CFC) on risk vs security trade-off and behavioral intention and thus, provide some implications for improving mobile commerce adoption. From the practical perspective, this study provides managers with significant insights of how to develop and promote mobile commerce in Vietnam.

3. Methodology

Previous studies on mobile commerce context in a Vietnam context

Although mobile commerce is becoming a global phenomenon, attracting the immense interest of scholars, Vietnam still lacks academic studies regarding how the intention to use mobile commerce is formed and consolidated. Table 2-2 summarizes notable research on mobile commerce adoption which is conducted in

a Vietnam context. These includes the studies of Phong et al. (2018), Khoi et al. (2018), Nguyễn Hữu Khôi (2019), Choi and Mai (2018), Dinh, Nguyen and Nguyen (2018), Lin and Nguyen (2011), Nguyen and Anh Nguyen (2016) and Phuong, Ngoc and Dai Trang (2018).

Phong et al. (2018) use the Theory of Reason Action as a fundamental framework to investigate not only the driving forces of mobile shopping behaviors but also the barrier sides of the mobile business. In particular, this study treats attitude, subjective norm, trust and self-efficacy as promoters while the perception of risk and cost as barriers. To test the hypotheses, they adopt a structural equation modeling approach on a survey data of 208 Vietnamese consumers. The results of this study demonstrate that TRA has predictive power in explaining consumer behavior in a mobile shopping context. Also, additional promotion and barrier variables demonstrate a strong influence on the intention to adopt mobile shopping. Khoi et al. (2018) integrate three types of perceived values including utilitarian, hedonic and social value into the Theory of Planned Behavior to test the direct and indirect effects of these values on behavioral intention. This study is conducted to understand how consumers' intention to adopt mobile commerce is formed in a developing country, Vietnam. To test the hypotheses, they adopt a structural equation modeling approach on sample of 382 Vietnamese consumers. The testing results indicate that three types of value have a direct and indirect influence on attitudes and intention to adopt mobile commerce. Nguyễn Hữu Khôi (2019) conducted a study to fill the gap in generating a more comprehensive understanding regarding the relationship between perceived value components and between perceived values and behavioral intention in mobile commerce context. Accordingly, epistemic value and conditional value are hypothesized to have impacts on utilitarian, hedonic and social value. Also, these perceived values are hypothesized to have an influence on the intention to use mobile commerce. The testing results on a sample of 350 mobile services consumers with SmartPLS indicate that except the impact of social value on behavioral intention and the influence of conditional value on hedonic value are insignificant, the remaining hypotheses are supported by data. With those interesting results, this study has contributions in both academic and practical ways.

The summarization of previous studies in a Vietnam context, including independent variables, mediator and/or moderator variables and dependent variables as well as key findings are examined and presented in Table 2-2 to form a comprehensive view of mobile commerce research in the Vietnam context.

Table 1: Previous studies on mobile commerce in a Vietnam context

No.	Author(s)	Independent variable(s)	Mediator/ Moderator variable(s)	Dependent variable(s)	Findings
1	Phong et al. (2018)	TRA's variables, promotion factors: perceived trust, self-efficacy; barrier factors: perceived risk and perceived cost.		Intention to adopt mobile commerce	TRA's variables have positive effects on intention to adopt mobile commerce; promotion factors have positive effects while barrier have negative effects on intention to adopt mobile commerce
2	Khoi et al. (2018)	Perceived behavioral control utilitarian, hedonic and social values	Mediators: Attitude toward mobile commerce, subjective norms	Intention to adopt mobile commerce	TPB's variables have positive effects on intention to use mobile commerce; Utilitarian and hedonic have direct and indirect effect on intention to adopt mobile commerce.
3	Nguyễn Hữu Khôi (2019)	Epistemic value, conditional value	Mediators: Utilitarian, hedonic and social values	Intention to use mobile commerce	Except for the impact of social value on the intention to use mobile commerce and the influence of conditional value on hedonic value, the remaining effects are supported by data.

No.	Author(s)	Independent variable(s)	Mediator/ Moderator variable(s)	Dependent variable(s)	Findings
4	Choi and Mai (2018)	e-service quality: usefulness, convenience, security, responsiveness, assurance	e-Trust	Consumer loyalty	Except for the impact of security on loyalty, all the remaining influences are supported by data.
5	Dinh et al. (2018)	Conceptual research in order to explore motivations and barriers of mobile payment adoption			integrated marketing communications can foster the adoption of mobile payment services in Vietnam
6	Lin and Nguyen (2011)	Motivation: perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use Uncertainty: perceived risk, information on e-payment	Moderators: personal innovativeness in technology	E-payment use	Motivation factors have positive effects while uncertainty factors have negative effects on e-payment use. Also, the moderating effects are supported by data
7	Han, Thao Nguyen and Anh Nguyen (2016)	Personal innovativeness, system quality, content quality, service quality, perceived cost	Mediators: perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived playfulness. Moderators: gender, hedonic and utilitarian tendencies	Intention to use, mobile commerce usage	Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and perceived playfulness have positive effects on intention to use mobile commerce while perceived cost has a negative effect on mobile commerce use. Personal innovativeness, system quality, and content quality have positive effects on perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and perceived playfulness. The moderating effects of gender, utilitarian and hedonic tendencies are also supported.
8	Phuong et al. (2018)	Service quality, system quality, information quality	Mediators: overall perceived service quality, customer satisfaction	Online repurchase intention	Service quality, system quality, and information quality have positive effects on overall perceived service quality which in turn, has a positive influence on customer satisfaction. Finally, customer satisfaction has a positive impact on repurchase intention.

From the summarization presented in Table 2-2, some insights can be extracted. Firstly, previous studies in a Vietnam context have mainly focused on the initial intention to adopt mobile commerce while continuance intention to use mobile commerce has received less attention. Previous studies agreed that consumers' loyalty, repurchase intention, and continuance intention to use mobile commerce are vital to the sustainable development of this innovative type of commerce (Zhou, 2013c, Zhou, 2013e, Zhou, 2014). In other words, unless consumers continue their mobile commerce usage, mobile commerce service providers cannot achieve

success (Chong, 2015). As such, identifying and testing the factors affecting continuance intention to use mobile commerce is significant in retaining consumers, fostering businesses to recover their cost and to make a profit. Thus, this study focus on continuance intention rather than the initial adoption of mobile commerce in a Vietnam context.

The literature review of previous studies in a Vietnam context indicates that scholars have utilized well-established models such as TPB, TRA, MISS and some other classical model such as TAM with extended variables such as consumers' perceptions (e.g., values, cost, benefit) to explain and predict behavioral intention to use mobile commerce. The findings of these studies, while demonstrating that TPB, TRA, MISS, and TAM can be useful to explain consumer behavioral intention in a Vietnam context, also show that consumers' perceptions have significant and strong effects on consumers' intention and behavior of using mobile commerce. As such, this study expects that consumers' perceptions also have a vital role in explaining continuance intention to use mobile commerce. This expectation is supported by the findings of previous studies which demonstrate that consumers' perception such as trust, risk, and security (Chong, 2015, Nabavi et al., 2016, Yuan et al., 2014, Zhou, 2014). Also, previous studies have generated a call for investigating both promotion and barrier factors in one research in order to clearly understand how these contradicted determinants affect consumers' intention and behavior (Phong et al., 2018). Furthermore, there exists evidence demonstrating that the perceptions of promotion and barrier factors are different between developed and developing countries (Hanafizadeh et al., 2014, Malaquias and Hwang, 2016). As such, there is a need to integrate both promotion and barrier factors into a research model to better understand continuance intention to use mobile commerce in a Vietnam context. In this context, while perceived risk has been investigated in some studies (Nguyễn Hữu Khôi and Hồ Huy Tựu, 2017, Phong et al., 2018), perceived security has been largely ignored. Thus, this study adopts perceived risk and security to delineate a research model to explain continuance intention to use mobile commerce. This is because while risk and security perception are widely accepted as important determinants of continuance intention to use mobile commerce (Chong, 2015, Nabavi et al., 2016, Zhou, 2014), there is a lack of studies utilizes both these constructs to explain repurchase intention, espically in a mobile commerce context. Also, this study go a step further in providing a deeper and broader understanding of how perceived risk and security affect continuance intention to use mobile commerce by adopting a multi-dimensional approach to conceptualize these constructs.

Finally, previous studies have emphasized the importance of the individual difference or personality trait variables in explaining consumer behavior (Parks-Leduc, Feldman and Bardi, 2015). For example, Walczuch and Lundgren (2004), Devaraj, Easley and Crant (2008) and Junglas, Johnson and Spitzmüller (2008) have adopted Big Five personality traits to explain consumers' acceptance of innovative technologies while Citrin, Sprott, Silverman and Stem (2000), Agarwal, Ahuja, Carter and Gans (1998) and Zhang et al. (2012) integrate personal innovativeness to explain consumer's adoption of information technology and information system. However, these variables have been received less attention of Vietnamese scholars. This generates a gap in understanding if and how individual difference or personality trait variables directly and interactively affects consumers' perception such as perceived risk and security and consumer behavioral intention such as continuance intention to use mobile commerce. This study focuses on CFC, an important variable in explaining consumer behavior (Joireman et al., 2012, Strathman et al., 1994) which is largely ignored in a Vietnam context. This is because while CFC have been utilized successfully to explain (un)healthy eating behavior in a Vietnam context (Olsen and Tuu, 2017), yet this construct is largely ignored in a mobile commerce context, especially in Vietnam. Therefore, the integration of CFC into a research model to explain consumers' perceptions of risk and security and continuance intention to use mobile can bring more insights of how to foster and maintain consumers.

To sum up, from a Vietnam perspective, this study contributes in three-fold. Firstly, the current study explains continuance intention to use mobile to provide insights into how to foster consumers' loyalty toward mobile commerce. Secondly, we simultaneously examine the role of perceived risk and security in explaining continuance intention to use mobile commerce. Finally, we also explain continuance intention to use mobile

commerce and consumers' perception of risk and security from a consideration of future consequences perspective.

b. Previous studies on mobile commerce in an international context

The rapid development of mobile technologies and mobiles devices have fostered the emergence of a wide range of mobile services such as mobile banking (Shaikh and Karjaluoto, 2015), mobile TV (Choi and Totten, 2012), mobile marketing (Persaud and Azhar, 2012), mobile learning (Park, 2011), mobile entertainment (game, music) and mobile transaction (making purchase, reservation) (Ovčjak et al., 2015). As such, the acceptance of mobile technology has become a very significant topic (Sanakulov and Karjaluoto, 2015, Shaikh and Karjaluoto, 2015). Thus, a remarkable amount of scholars has put their effort into explaining the mobile technologies and services adoption process and as a result, a wide range of determinants of mobile services have been proposed and tested (Gerpott and Thomas, 2014, Zhang et al., 2012). Those findings have made significant contributions to modern mobile services adopted research in both theoretical and practical ways.

Past studies (e.g., Chong et al., 2012, Khalifa and Shen, 2008b, Wei, Marthandan, Chong, Ooi and Arumugam, 2009) used a variety of theories and models to predict behavioral intention to adopt mobile commerce. According to past systematic literature review and meta-analysis studies (Gerpott and Thomas, 2014, Ovčjak et al., 2015, Shaikh and Karjaluoto, 2015, Zhang et al., 2012), most of widely adopted theories are theory of reasoned action (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980, Fishbein and Ajzen, 1977), Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), technology acceptance model (Davis, 1989), information systems success (DeLone and McLean, 1992, DeLone and McLean, 2003), innovation diffusion theory (Rogers, 1995), the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003), and extended models based on these theories (e.g., Khalifa et al., 2012, Khalifa and Shen, 2008b). Table 2-3 summarizes some widely adopted theories and their main characteristics.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.: Some widely adopted theories of adoption

Models	Authors	Description
Theory of reasoned behavior (TRA)	Ajzen and Fishbein (1980), Fishbein and Ajzen (1977)	Individuals' intention to adopt new technology and information system is predicted by their attitude (toward the new technology and information system) and subjective norms
Theory of planned behavior (TPB)	Ajzen (1991)	Based on the theory of reasoned action with the addition of perceived behavioral control. Accordingly, behavioral intention is a function of attitudes, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control.
Technology acceptance model (TAM)	Davis (1989)	Bases on the theory of reasoned action, Davis (1989) developed the technology acceptance model which postulates that intention to adopt new technology of individuals is influenced by perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use.
Model of information system success (MISS)	DeLone and McLean (1992), DeLone and McLean (2003)	According to this model, the success of an IS system is influenced by six factors, including information quality, system quality, system use, user satisfaction, individual impact, and organizational impact.
Innovation diffusion theory (IDT)	Rogers (1995)	This process of innovation adoption includes five stages: acquiring knowledge, forming attitude, deciding to adopt, implementing the new idea and confirming the decision.
Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT)	Venkatesh et al. (2003)	According to UTAUT, the intention to adopt new technology is influenced by three main factors including performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence. Furthermore, the actual adoption of this new technology is affected by behavioral intention and facilitating conditions.
Social cognitive theory (SCT)	Bandura (1986)	SCT comprises three sets of factors: environmental factors, personal factors, and behaviors.
The extended unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT2)	Venkatesh, Thong and Xu (2012)	UTAUT with the incorporation of three other constructs, including hedonic motivation, price value, and habit.

Models	Authors	Description
Task – technology fit (TTF)	Goodhue and Thompson (1995)	Innovative technologies are more likely to be adopted if their capabilities match the tasks that the user must perform.

4. Results

The theory of reasoned action (TRA) theory is originally proposed by Fishbein and Ajzen (1977) and Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) have further improved it. TRA is considered the most widely used theory to explain behaviors in a wide range of contexts (Ajzen, 2012, Fishbein and Ajzen, 2011), including mobile services and mobile commerce (Gerpott and Thomas, 2014, Nabavi et al., 2016, Zhang et al., 2012). Although several rival theories of TRA were proposed (TAM, MISS or UTAUT) to explain consumer's behavior in the context of mobile commerce, TRA is still a robust and parsimonious model that is widely adopted in predicting a wide range of individuals' behaviors over time (Bagozzi, 2007, Benbasat and Barki, 2007). Evidence comes from hundreds of studies that have been summarized in several meta-analyses and reviews indicating that TRA theory has been proven to be effective and efficient in fostering the understanding of consumer reasoned action (Albarracin, Johnson, Fishbein and Muellerleile, 2001, Sheeran and Taylor, 1999), particularly toward consumption of e-services such as mobile commerce (Gerpott and Thomas, 2014, Nabavi et al., 2016, Sanakulov and Karjaluo, 2015, Zhang et al., 2012). Based on TRA, Ajzen (1991) has developed the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) to explain individual behavior. Similar to TRA, TPB has been widely used by academia to predict the adoption of innovative services such as mobile commerce (Gerpott and Thomas, 2014, Nabavi et al., 2016, Ovčjak et al., 2015, Zhang et al., 2012). It is worthy to note that TPB and its antecedent (i.e., TRA; Fishbein and Ajzen, 2011) have been adopted to examine a wide range of behaviors, including behavior in information systems, electronic commerce and mobile commerce context (Ajzen, 2012). Thus, it is one of the most-used cognitive models in explaining individuals' behaviors. Adopting TRA as a fundamental framework, Davis (1989) proposed the TAM model for explaining the behavior of technology adoption. In the context of mobile services and technologies, TAM has been extensively adopted to predict consumer behavior (Gerpott and Thomas, 2014, Nabavi et al., 2016, Sanakulov and Karjaluo, 2015, Zhang et al., 2012). According to Davis (1989), intention to adopt new technology of individuals is influenced by perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Previous studies have confirmed the robustness and parsimony of TAM (Ovčjak et al., 2015, Shaikh and Karjaluo, 2015). The model of information systems success (MISS) is proposed by DeLone and McLean (1992) and one of the most widely adopted models in the context of information system (IS) (Sharkey, Scott and Acton, 2010, Teo, Srivastava and Jiang, 2008). According to this model, the success of an IS system is influenced by six factors, including information quality, system quality, system use, user satisfaction, individual impact, and organizational impact (DeLone and McLean, 1992). Innovation diffusion theory (IDT) is originally developed in 1960 to explain how new technologies impact consumption behaviors in contemporary society (Rogers, 1995). According to Rogers (1995), innovation refers to any set of new ideas, concepts or applications and innovation diffusion is a communicating process through which innovation is recognized and shared by individuals. Therefore, a new technology may or may not be adopted depending on the innovation-decision process. This process includes five stages: acquiring knowledge, forming attitude, deciding to adopt, implementing the new idea and confirming decision. Rogers (1995) also posits that the success of innovation diffusion process is dependent on the five significant categories of innovations characteristics: relative advantages, compatibility, complexity, trialability, observability. These five characteristics have important role in explaining the consumer's decision-making process, and are adopted by scholars to investigate the acceptance of innovative services and technology (Cheng, 2017, Im and Ha, 2012, Moore and Benbasat, 1991). Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) is developed based on the conceptual and empirical synthesis of widely adopted models in the field of technology acceptance such as TAM, TPB, social cognitive theory, IDT in order to provide a coherent theoretical perspective in studying innovation adoption (Venkatesh et al., 2003). According to UTAUT, the intention to adopt a new technology is influenced by three main factors including performance expectancy, effort expectancy and social influence. Furthermore, actual adoption of this new technology is affected by behavioral intention and facilitating

conditions. While performance expectancy is proposed to have a direct effect on behavioral intention (Celik, 2016, Kijisanayotin, Pannarunothai and Speedie, 2009, Liu et al., 2015, Venkatesh et al., 2003), this relationship is also proposed to be moderated by gender and age. Effort expectancy can be seen as the perceived complexity of the technology and the degree of energy needed to use it. As proposed by UTAUT, the effort expectancy has a direct effect on behavioral intention (Celik, 2016, Kijisanayotin et al., 2009, Liu et al., 2015, Venkatesh et al., 2003, Williams, Rana and Dwivedi, 2015) and this relationship is moderated by gender, age and experience. Also according these authors, the relationship between social influences and behavioral intention is moderate by gender, age, experience and voluntariness. Finally, the relationship between facilitating conditions and actual behavior is proposed to be moderated by age and experience (Venkatesh et al., 2003).

Social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1986) aims at explaining an individual's motivations, thoughts, and behavior in a wide range of contexts including within the context of social interactions, experiences, and outside media influences. According to this theory, behavior and reproduction of this behavior are influenced by the interaction between three main factors, which are environmental influences, cognition/ personal factors. In other words, individuals perform a behavior and observe the consequences which in turn, are used to guide subsequent behavior. Also, individuals do not only react to environmental influences but also act to positively create and justify their environment which in turn, influences their cognition and how they would change the environment. As such, the behavior they perform determine their cognition and the environment. UTAUT model aims to improve UTAUT to fit the consumer technology use context by integrating hedonic motivation, price value, and habit into UTAUT. Hedonic motivation is the fun or pleasure of using technology while price value is consumers' cognitive trade-off between the perceived benefits of using new technology and the monetary cost of using that new technology. Finally, habit is the extent to which people tend to perform behaviors automatically because of learning. The theory of TTF is one of the widely used theories in explaining information system adoption. According to this theory, a technology or an information system will gain acceptance from individuals when it is useful and presents a good fit for the tasks that people perform. A technology could be considered as a tool that supports individuals perform their tasks (e.g., computer system, electronic commerce, mobile commerce) while a task is the actions to be performed by individuals to achieve certain outputs. Task-technology fit occurs when is useful in assisting individuals in performing their tasks. Performance impact relates to the results of performing tasks by individuals and utilization is the behavior of adopting the new technology in performing tasks.

These theories have been adopted, utilized and extended in many previous studies. For example, TAM is adopted in the studies of Yang (2005), Cheong and Park (2005) and Wu and Wang (2005). IDT is used in the studies of Hung, Ku and Chang (2003) and Mallat, Rossi, Tuunainen and Öörni (2008). TRA and TPB play an important role in the studies of Khalifa and Shen (2008a) and Khalifa and Shen (2008b). Furthermore, these theories have been used to explain a wide range of mobile services and mobile commerce usage. More specifically, TAM has been adopted to explain mobile learning, mobile shopping, mobile gaming and mobile TV (Jung, Perez-Mira and Wiley-Patton, 2009, Liu and Li, 2011, Park, 2011); UTAUT has been used to explain acceptance of mobile data services, mobile banking, tablets, mobile location-based services (Lu, Yu and Liu, 2009, Yoon, 2009, Zhou, 2012); TPB have been utilized to study mobile commerce adoption or mobile learning (Cheon, Lee, Crooks and Song, 2012, Khalifa and Shen, 2008a). According to recent literature review and meta-analysis (Ovčjak et al., 2015, Sanakulov and Karjaluo, 2015, Shaikh and Karjaluo, 2015, Zhang et al., 2012), TAM is the most widely adopted theory to explain mobile commerce and service adoption, following by TRA and TPB. UTAUT, IDT, and MISS are also among the extensively adopted models.

However, TAM, TRA, and TPB are also criticized by scholars due to critical limitations. For example, TRA addresses purely volitional control and fails to address the owning of requisite opportunities and resources (Madden, Ellen and Ajzen, 1992). Therefore, the neglect of non-volitional factors (e.g. resources, skills or confidence) for predicting and explaining individuals' behaviors raises the question of the applicability of TRA (Han, Hsu and Sheu, 2010). In other words, the successful application of the TRA theory in explaining specific behaviors depends on the degree to which the behavior is volitional (i.e., individuals have major control over the behavior in question). Thus, it is not clear that the TRA components are sufficient to predict behaviors in

which volitional control is reduced. Furthermore, TRA is not primarily tailored for information systems studies such as mobile commerce (Wei et al., 2009). As a result, TRA also does not contain some significant variables that have the potential to explain consumers' behaviors in a mobile commerce context, for example, risk (Pavlou, 2003) or security perception (Chang and Chen, 2009, Hartono et al., 2014). Therefore, studies on the intention to use mobile commerce improve the predictive power of TRA by integrating extensive variables (Gerpott and Thomas, 2014, Nabavi et al., 2016, Sanakulov and Karjaluoto, 2015, Zhang et al., 2012). Regarding TPB, it is designed to explain individuals' intention and behavior in a general context and thus, it should be revised or extended to increase predictive power in a specific context. For example, prior studies have extended TPB by decomposing its components (Pavlou and Fygenson, 2006) or by adding additional components (Khoi et al., 2018). However, TPB is one of the most adopted models to explain consumer behavior in a mobile commerce context (Gerpott and Thomas, 2014, Zhang et al., 2012). TAM has some limitations in explaining behavioral intention in the context of mobile commerce. Firstly, what the consumer chooses to adopt in mobile commerce is not merely a technology per se, but rather a new channel of commerce. In other words, mobile commerce adoption goes beyond the realm of traditional marketing, and it must thus be understood from the viewpoint that online consumers are simultaneously information systems (IS) users (Koufaris, 2002). This generates the need to extend TAM to effectively predict behavioral intention in the context of mobile commerce. Secondly, TAM lacks barriers (Mathieson, Peacock and Chin, 2001) and does not account for social influence in the adoption and utilization of new information systems. This limitation seems particularly disturbing when adoption decisions relating to mobile commerce (Malhotra and Galletta, 1999). Thirdly, TAM assumes that IS adoption is volitional. It means there are no barriers that prevent consumers from using a mobile commerce if they chose to do so. This fact has drawn criticism from researchers (e.g., Mathieson et al., 2001) and urged some scholars to extend the TAM to include perceived risks as an antecedent to the adoption of mobile commerce. Similarly, Pavlou (2003) emphasizes the fact that Internet transaction has introduced uncertainty and risk. He also validates the need for integration of trust and perceived risk into existing models of technology adoption as direct antecedents of intention to transact online.

5. Conclusion

To overcome these limitations and increase the predictive power of proposed research models, previous studies have tried to combine theories together to form a more comprehensive model to explain consumers' behavior (Ovčjak et al., 2015). For example, López-Nicolása, Molina-Castilloa and Bouwman (2008) have integrated TAM and IDT to explain the acceptance of advanced mobile services. Kim, Jin Ma and Park (2009) have combined TAM and TRA to form a model predicting the adoption of mobile technologies for fashion goods. A more widely used approach is that scholars extend theories with additional constructs (Faqih and Jaradat, 2015, Sun, Wang and Cao, 2009, Zhang et al., 2012). According to recent meta-analyses and systematic literature review (Gerpott and Thomas, 2014, Ovčjak et al., 2015, Sanakulov and Karjaluoto, 2015, Shaikh and Karjaluoto, 2015, Zhang et al., 2012), individual difference variables have important role in explaining consumer behavior in a mobile commerce context and could be integrate into fundamental framework such as TAM, TRA or TPB to increase predictive power (Lu, 2014, Lu, Yao and Yu, 2005). For example, in their meta-analyses, Gerpott and Thomas (2014) and Zhang et al. (2012) indicated that personal innovativeness had a strong impact on mobile internet usage. This finding is consistent with previous findings in systematic review studies (Sanakulov and Karjaluoto, 2015, Shaikh and Karjaluoto, 2015) demonstrating that personal innovativeness is one of the most significant individual traits that have an important impact on mobile service adoption. These results suggest that individual difference variables have important role in explaining consumers' behavior in a mobile commerce context and researcher should investigate further to explore more individual difference variables in explaining consumers' behavior such as continuance intention to use mobile commerce (Gerpott and Thomas, 2014, Sanakulov and Karjaluoto, 2015, Shaikh and Karjaluoto, 2015, Zhang et al., 2012). Also, previous studies have demonstrated the perceived risk and trust or perceived security has significant impacts on consumers' behavior in a mobile commerce context (Ovčjak et al., 2015, Zhang et al., 2012). Indeed, these variables have strong and opposite influences on intention to use mobile services (Ovčjak

et al., 2015, Zhang et al., 2012). As such, it is suggested that perceived risk and security will have important role in explaining continuance intention to use mobile commerce. In the next two section,

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